

National Leprosy Conference 2025

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Abstract Book

Ministry of Health

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SASAKAWA
LEPROSY
INITIATIVE

PP-5: Synergizing Curative and Preventive Actions: Monthly Leprosy Summary Report of Regional Director of Health Services Area- Colombo

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Background

In the context of leprosy control, services of curative sector dermatology clinics as well as field-level interventions led by Medical Officer of health (MOH) teams play mutually beneficial critical roles. Dermatology clinics serve as key entry points for diagnosis, treatment initiation, and follow-up care, while MOH field teams ensure continuity through contact screening, tracing of defaulters, and community-level suspected-case detection. Delays in data transfer and limited integration of clinic-based and community-level activities could potentially hinder timely follow-up and contact screening. To address these gaps, a standardized monthly reporting summary was developed to synchronize efforts across both sectors.

Description of the initiative

A comprehensive summary template to collate all domains of leprosy prevention and control was developed with the expert inputs including that of Anti Leprosy Campaign. The Monthly Leprosy Control Summary for the Colombo district consolidates surveillance and operational data from dermatology clinics and MOH areas to monitor leprosy case detection, follow-up, and contact screening activities. This report captures clinic-level metrics such as patient attendance, new case registrations, H544 form submissions, defaulter follow-ups, and contact screening outcomes. It also documents administrative processes including the filing of green copies at the RDHS office and the dispatch of red copies to the Anti-Leprosy Campaign (ALC), along with updates to the district register. Parallely, field-level activities across MOH areas are tracked to ensure timely receipt of notifications, tracing of missing records, and effective contact screening. The summary also includes data on referrals from MOH offices to dermatology clinics and the diagnostic yield of these referrals.

Methods Used for the Evaluation

This summary is used in review meetings across national, provincial and district levels.

Results

The introduction of the monthly leprosy control format has considerably improved coordination between curative services and MOH field teams. At the end of each month, the summary report is sent to the national level. Tallying the curative and preventive sector data has enabled detecting any discrepancy thus improving the coverage and timeliness indicators.

Lessons Learnt

A consolidated summary report across curative and preventive sectors enables streamlining data collection, ensuring timely reporting and facilitating the integration of clinic-based and field-level leprosy control efforts.